

A Study to Evaluate the Effectiveness of Structured Teaching Programme on Mechanical Ventilator Care Teaching among the GNM Second Year Students in Selected Nursing School at Shahjahanpur, Uttar Pradesh

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Abstract:-

Introduction: A mechanical ventilator is a device which is used to improve breathing of a person by providing proper amount of oxygen in a long time basis.

Objective: To evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme on mechanical ventilator care teaching among the GNM second year students in selected nursing school at Shahjahanpur.

Design: A quantitative approach using pre experimental one group pre and post test design.

Samples: 30 students of G.N.M IInd year who are presented in the Florence nightingale school of nursing Shahjahanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

Intervention: Providing education with structured teaching programme regarding ventilator care among the GNM second year students in selected nursing school at Shahjahanpur.

Tool: Standardized 30 structured questionnaires for evaluating the level of knowledge regarding ventilator care.

Result: Data Analysis among Experimental group (30 students of GNM II nd year) by using paired't' test found significant value 94.72 at $p < 0.05$ level.

Conclusion: The intervention (structured teaching programme) is good to increasing the knowledge level of ventilator care among GNM second year students in selected nursing school at, Shahjahanpur.

I. INTRODUCTION

Mechanical ventilator is an artificial assisted device aids in improving the breathing pattern of a person. The main aim of mechanical ventilator is to improve oxygenation. It is mainly divided into positive pressure and negative pressure ventilator with different modes. The main purpose of providing mechanical ventilation is to protect the lungs and improve oxygenation to all the vital organs. The health care providers mainly doctors and nurses should have through

knowledge about the function of mechanical ventilator and how to care the patient in ventilator.

II. PROBLEM STATEMENT

“A STUDY TO EVALUATE THE EFFECTIVENESS OF STRUCTURED TEACHING PROGRAMME ON MECHANICAL VENTILATOR CARE TEACHING AMONG THE GNM SECOND YEAR STUDENTS IN SELECTED NURSING SCHOOL AT SHAHJAHANPUR, UTTAR PRADESH”

III. OBJECTIVE OF STUDY

- To assess the pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding mechanical ventilator care among GNM second year students in selected nursing school at Shahjahanpur.
- To evaluate the effectiveness of structured teaching programme regarding Mechanical Ventilator Care among GNM second year students in selected nursing school at Shahjahanpur.
- To find out the association between on socio demographic variable and the knowledge about Mechanical Ventilator Care among GNM second year students in selected nursing school at Shahjahanpur.

IV. HYPOTHESIS

The hypothesis is tested of level 0.05 of significance.

The hypothesis used in this study are –

- H1: There will a significant difference between the pre- test and post-test level of knowledge about Mechanical Ventilator Care among the GNM second year students in selected nursing school at Shahjahanpur.
- H2: There will be a significant association between the levels of knowledge scores with their selected demographic variable.
- H0: There will be no significant difference between pre-test and post-test level of knowledge regarding Mechanical Ventilator Care among the GNM second year students in selected nursing school at Shahjahanpur.

V. METHODOLOGY

A. RESEARCH APPROACH

In this study quantitative research approach will be utilized.

B. RESEARCH DESIGN

The research design which is utilized i.e One group pre-test post-test pre experimental research design.

C. SETTING OF THE STUDY

The setting of the study was, at Florence Nightingale School of nursing at Shahjahanpur.

D. SAMPLING TECHNIQUE

The sampling technique will be used are non probability sampling technique i.e. purposive sampling technique.

E. SAMPLE

The sample of the study is students of G.N.M IInd year Florence nightingale school of nursing Shahjahanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

F. SAMPLE SIZE

Sample size used is 30 students of G.N.M IInd year who are presented in the Florence nightingale school of nursing Shahjahanpur, Uttar Pradesh.

G. TOOL

- PART-1. It consisted of Demographic variables of age, gender, knowledge, education status, residential area, source of knowledge year of study about ventilator care working area and religion.
- PART-2. It consists of 30 structured knowledge questionnaires regarding mechanical ventilator care.

VI. RESULT

A. SECTION 1: FREQUENCY PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION BASED ON DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLE AMONG GNM SECOND YEAR STUDENTS

Table 1: Frequency Percentage Distribution Based on Demographic Variable Among GNM Second Year Students

SR. NO.	DEMOGRAPHIC VARIABLES	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
1	AGE		
	18-20 year	16	53.3%
	21-23 year	10	33.3%
	24-26 year	2	6.6%
	Above 27 year	2	6.6%
2	GENDER		
	Female	26	86.6%
	Male	4	13.3%
3	RESIDENTIAL AREA		
	Urban	18	60%
	Rural	12	40%
4	TYPES OF FAMILY		
	Joint	14	46.6%
	Nuclear	16	53.3%
5	RELIGION		
	Hindu	28	93.3%
	Muslim	2	6.6%
	Sikh	0	0%
	Christian	0	0%
6	EDUCATION STATUS		
	GNM	30	100%
	B.Sc	0	0%
	Post B.Sc	0	0%
7	SOURCE OF KNOWLEDGE		
	Mass media	4	13.3%
	Health education	6	20%
	Book	16	53.3%
	Family and relative	3	10%
8	YEAR OF STUDY		
	GNM Ist	0	0%
	GNM IInd	30	100%
	GNM IIIrd	0	0%

B. SECTION-II: FREQUENCY, PERCENTAGE AND DISTRIBUTION OF PRE- TEST AND POST- TEST LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE.

Table 2: Frequency, Percentage And Distribution Of Pre- Test And Post- Test Level Of Knowledge N=30

LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE	PRE-TEST SCORE		POST-TEST SCORE	
	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE	FREQUENCY	PERCENTAGE
POOR LEVEL	20	67%	0	0%
AVERAGE LEVEL	9	29%	7	18%
GOOD LEVEL	1	4%	23	82%

Fig. 1(a)

Fig. 1(b) FREQUENCY AND PERCENTAGE DISTRIBUTION OF PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST LEVEL OF KNOWLEDGE

C. SECTION-III: - MEAN, STANDARD DEVIATION (SD) AND 't' VALUE BETWEEN PRE-TEST AND POST-TEST KNOWLEDGE

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation (SD) And 'T' Value Between Pre-Test and Post-Test Knowledge

GROUP	MEAN	S.D	MEAN DIFFERENCE	't' VALUE	't' cal VALUE	SIGNIFICANCE
PRE-TEST	10.03	1.73	11.8	2.05	94.72	Significant
POST-TEST	21.83	1.81				

VII. CONCLUSION

The conclusion which was identified from the present study most of the GNM IInd year students had poor and average knowledge regarding mechanical ventilator care in pre test and good and average knowledge regarding mechanical ventilator care in post test. This indicate that the structured teaching programme regarding mechanical ventilator care was good at improving knowledge among GNM II year students of Florence Nightingale school of nursing, shahjahanpur.

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